

Clinical Profile and Treatment Modalities in Atrophic Rhinitis: A Descriptive Study

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Abstract:

Introduction: Atrophic rhinitis is a chronic nasal disease characterized by progressive atrophy of the mucosa and underlying bone of the turbinates and the presence of a viscid secretion which rapidly dries and forms crusts which emit characteristic foul odor sometimes called ozaena. The objective of the study aimed to describe the clinical presentation of atrophic rhinitis, various modalities of treatment and clinical response to the treatment at our tertiary care centre.

Methods: The clinical profile of the patients was categorized into symptoms and signs of the disease. The various modalities of treatment employed were, Alkaline nasal douching in 14 patients, nasal douching followed by 25% glucose in glycerine nasal drops in 10, modified Young's surgery in 8, endoscopic neoturbinate surgery in 3 patients. Follow up period was 6 months.

Results: The patients who undergone alkaline nasal douching, satisfactory response seen in 8 (57.1%) and unsatisfactory response in 6 (42.9%) patients. Patients with nasal douching and 25% glucose in glycerine nasal drops 8 (80%) had satisfactory response and 2 (20%) unsatisfactory. Among patients with modified Young's surgery showed satisfactory response in 6 (75%) patients. Endoscopic neoturbinate surgery showed satisfactory response in 2 (66.6%) patients.

Conclusion: The results are encouraging with healthier mucosa, reduced crusting and foul odour. In spite of tireless efforts, as etiology still remains unexplained, management of the disease done with various medical regimens and various surgical procedures. Surgical options for the disease are also not completely satisfactory.

Keywords: Atrophic rhinitis, Young's surgery, Saddle nose deformity, Myiasis, Neoturbinate.

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Introduction

Atrophic rhinitis is a distressing malady of nose characterized by progressive atrophy of the mucosa and underlying bones of the turbinates resulting in abnormal patency of the nasal passages. [1] Nearly one and a half century ago, in 1876 Fraenkel first described this chronic distressing condition, incurable yet not fatal. Fraenkel described atrophic rhinitis as a chronic nasal disease, characterized by a triad of symptoms, namely foul odour, atrophy of nasal mucosa and crusts formation. [2]

Atrophic rhinitis (AR) is of two types: primary and secondary. Primary AR is rare in the Developed countries. Most cases are reported in China, Egypt, and India. Microbiology of primary AR is almost uniformly presence of Klebsiella ozaenae.

The disease has a slowly progressing debilitating course. Histopathological changes in atrophic rhinitis are squamous metaplasia, chronic inflammatory cellular infiltrate, granulation tissue, reduced vascularity and a decrease in number or even absence of the mucosal glands. [3] Though

atrophic rhinitis is not a crippling disease which renders endanger to patients life, it causes a lot of suffering due to ozaena, anosmia, nasal obstruction, epistaxis, headache etc. The disease often left undiagnosed as the complaints are minor in early stages, is usually neglected by the patient. But the disease becomes a major illness particularly if it progress to complications such as septal perforation, palatal perforation, nasal deformity or myiasis. [4]

As the exact etiology is unknown, treatment is directed towards symptomatic relief. Medical treatment leads only to temporary remission of clinical features. Over the years, surgeons have attempted various techniques for long term relief of symptoms. Most of the techniques have been directed to the narrowing of the nasal cavity.

Inert foreign or synthetic materials have been implanted submucosally but this modality of the treatment has been purely temporary due to foreign materials being expelled from the nose in the due

course of time. [5] In this study we intend to describe the clinical presentation of atrophic rhinitis, the patients undergoing medical and surgical management at our tertiary care centre.

Materials and Methods

Study design: This descriptive study was conducted for a period of 3 years from January 2018 to December 2020 in otorhinolaryngology department at our tertiary care centre. A total of 35 patients with clinically diagnosed case of atrophic rhinitis were included in our study. Ethical clearance was obtained from Institutional ethical committee prior to the study. A written informed consent was obtained from the patients before their participation in the study.

Methodology: During the study period, the patients presented to otolaryngology OPD with clinical features of atrophic rhinitis were evaluated. Demographic data such as patient's age, sex, and socio economic status, laterality of infection, clinical symptoms and signs were recorded in standard proforma. The cases diagnosed as primary atrophic rhinitis were subjected to detailed history and examination. A routine haemogram (Hb%, TC, DC, BT, CT), urine examination (albumin, sugar, microscopy), ESR was done for the patients.

The following treatment modalities were employed and observed.

1) Alkaline nasal douching: Alkaline solution made by dissolving Sodium bicarbonate (28.4g), Sodium baborate (28.4g) and Sodium chloride (56.7g) in 280 ml of warm water to make the solution. Using plastic syringe nasal cavity is syringed with patient bending forwards saying K, K, K. Done 3-4 times/day till all crusts disappear.⁶ The solution loosens the crusts and removes discharge. The sample size was 14.

2) 25% Glucose in Glycerine: After crusts are removed, nose is painted with 25% glucose in glycerine, this preparation is instilled as nasal drops by patients.[6] Sample size was 10.

3) Modified Young's surgery: This surgery aims to partially close the nostrils.

Procedure: Under local anaesthesia, after local infiltration, Skin flaps are raised from medial and lateral walls of nasal vestibule, flaps are sutured together so as to completely close the nasal cavity, a central opening of 3mm size was maintained. Procedure was carried out bilaterally[7]. By this progress can be monitored with a nasal endoscope, also maintains physiological breathing. The sample size was 08.

4) Endoscopic neoturbinatotomy surgery. (Endoscope assisted transplantation of antral mucosa into nasal cavity): All the cases who were willing to undergo this surgery were taken for the study. The sample

size was 03. Apart from routine blood investigations for surgery, computed tomography (CT) scan of paranasal sinus was advised for the patients.

The CT changes of atrophic rhinitis as reported by Pace-Balzan et al. i.e (1) mucosal thickening of the paranasal sinuses, (2) loss of definition of the ostiomeatal complex, (3) hypoplasia of the maxillary sinuses, (4) enlargement of the nasal cavities with erosion and bowing of the lateral nasal wall, and (5) bony resorption and mucosal atrophy of the inferior and middle turbinates. These findings were observed in the patients and selected for the surgery[8].

Procedure: All the patients underwent the procedure under general anaesthesia. After local infiltration, a sublabial incision is taken and the canine fossa is exposed. The anterior wall of the maxilla is drilled using burr and a wide opening is made taking care that the mucoperiosteum of the antrum is not injured. Gradually, under endoscopic vision the whole of the maxillary sinus mucoperiosteum is separated from the bony cliffs and crevices using Freer's elevator or cottonoids dipped in 4% xylocaine with adrenaline. Uncinctomy is done to widen the ostium area then the elevated mucosa in the form of a sac is inverted and transplanted into the nasal cavity through the ostium with epithelial surface outwards and periosteal surface inwards. This inverted mucoperiosteal sac is bolgerized to septum by means of absorbable sutures. The maxillary sinus is again checked for bleeding areas, for no packing is inserted into the sinus or the nasal cavity.⁹

Post-operative care was taken by giving antibiotics, saline nasal douche to wash out the crusts and suction clearance of the nasal cavity to remove the crusts and look for the vitality of neoturbinatotomy. All the patients were followed up for a period of 6 months and clinical response was recorded.

Statistical Analysis: Data were pooled and analysed using SPSS v20 software.

Results

Our study included 35 patients. Age of the patients varied from 12 to 65years. The youngest patient was 12year female child. Majority of patients were in third decade of life (71.4%). In our study sex distribution showed female predominance (80%) than males (20%). 25 (71.4%) patients had bilateral infection. Incidence of atrophic rhinitis was more in patients of low socioeconomic status.

The clinical profile of the patients was categorized into symptoms and signs of the disease. The patients included in the study had chronic history of disease symptoms the duration of which was more than a year. The symptomatology of the patients included, nose block which was complained by 32

(91.4%) patients was the most common manifestation in our study. Other symptoms were purulent nasal discharge seen in 31 (88.5%), loss of smell sensation in 25 (71.4%), bleeding through the nose in 20 (57%), presence of maggots in 8 (22.8%) patients. Minor symptoms like dryness of nose, headache were also complained by the patients.

Among the nasal signs, foul smelling greenish crusts was seen in 30 (85.7%) patients, followed by roomy nasal cavity and atrophied nasal mucosa and atrophied turbinates in 28 (80%) of patients, deviated nasal septum in 25 and saddle nose deformity was seen in 6 (17%) patients. Demography and clinical profile of patients is shown in table 1.

In our study patients had undergone various modalities of treatment. Alkaline nasal douching in 14 (40%) patients, nasal douching followed by 25% glucose in glycerine nasal drops in 10 patients (28.57%), modified Young's surgery in 8 (22.8%) patients, endoscopic neoturbinate surgery in 3

(8.5%) patients. Patients were followed up for a period of 6 months. After treatment, patients were observed for symptoms and signs and were recorded. The clinical profile was categorized into improvement in subjective symptoms and objective signs. The clinical response was recorded as satisfactory or unsatisfactory in resolution of the illness. Criteria for clinical response after treatment are shown in table 2.

The patients who undergone alkaline nasal douching, satisfactory response seen in 8 (57.1%) and unsatisfactory response in 6 (42.9%) patients. Among patients with nasal douching and 25% glucose in glycerine nasal drops 8 (80%) patients had satisfactory response and 2 (20%) unsatisfactory. Among the surgically managed patients with modified Young's surgery showed satisfactory response in 6 (75%) patients.

Endoscopic neoturbinate surgery showed satisfactory response in 2 (66.6%) patients. Improvement in clinical profile after treatment is shown in table 3.

Table 1: Demography and Clinical profile of atrophic rhinitis

Variable	n (%)
Sex	
a. Male	7 (20)
b. Female	28 (80)
Infection	
a. Unilateral	10 (28.5)
b. Bilateral	25 (71.5)
Age (in years)	
0-20	3 (8.6)
21-40	25 (71.4)
41-60	6 (17.1)
>60	1 (2.8)
Clinical profile – Symptoms	
a. Nose block	32 (91.4)
b. Nasal discharge	31 (88.5)
c. Loss of smell sensation	25 (71.4)
d. Epistaxis	20 (57)
e. Myiasis	8 (22.8)
Clinical profile – Signs	
a. Foul smelling greenish crusts	30 (85.7)
b. Roomy nasal cavity	28 (80)
c. Atrophic mucosa and turbinates	28 (80)
d. Saddle nose deformity	6 (17.1)
Treatment modalities	
a. Alkaline nasal douching	14 (40)
b. Glucose in glycerine	10 (28.57)
c. Modified Young's surgery	8 (22.85)
d. Endoscopic neoturbinate surgery	3 (8.5)
Total	35 (100)

Table 2: Criteria for clinical response after treatment.

Improvement after treatment	
Subjective symptoms	Absence of nose block, dryness, purulent nasal discharge, headache, epistaxis, postnasal drip.
Objective signs	Absence of greenish crusts, presence of normal nasal pink mucosa, histological recovery of nasal epithelium.
Clinical response	
Satisfactory	Resolution of atleast 5 of subjective symptoms and atleast 2 of objective signs.
Unsatisfactory	Resolution of <5 subjective symptoms and <2 of objective signs.

Table 3: Improvement in Clinical profile after treatment.

Treatment modality	Satisfactory n (%)	Unsatisfactory n (%)	Total
a. Alkaline nasal douching	8 (57.1)	6 (42.9)	14
b. Glucose in glycerin	8 (80)	2 (20)	10
c. Modified young's surgery	6 (75)	2 (25)	8
d. Endoscopic neoturbinate	2 (66.6)	1 (33.3)	3

Discussion

Age of the patients varied from 12 to 65 years. The youngest patient was 12 year female child. Majority of patients were in third decade of life (71.4%). This can be correlated with study done by kedarnath et al [10] which showed patients aged between 19 and 65 years with a mean of 29.9 years.

In our study sex distribution showed female predominance (80%) than males (20%) which is similar to study done by Pampori et al, [11] female predominance was 77.7%. According to study done by Sharan R et al, [12] a male predominance of 85.7% was noted, which differ from our study. It seems that less caloric diet, early marriage, poor hygiene, and nonavailability of medical facilities in rural area are few causes why it is more common in rural females.

In our study, 25 (71.4%) patients had bilateral disease, according to Pampori et al, [11] bilaterality of the disease was 80% and unilateral in 20% which correlates with our study. Unilateral atrophic rhinitis had deviated nasal septum to the opposite side.

The symptomatology of the patients included, nose block which was complained by 32 (91.4%) patients was the most common manifestation in our study. Other symptoms were purulent nasal discharge seen in 31 (88.5%), loss of smell sensation in 25 (71.4%), bleeding through the nose in 20 (57%), presence of maggots in 8 (22.8%) patients.

In our study the majority of the patients presented with long duration of illness along with sequelae and complications of atrophic rhinitis such as saddle nose deformity, nasal myiasis and atrophic pharyngitis. This shows that primary atrophic rhinitis is a chronic disabling disease.

The anosmia occurs due to degeneration of nerve endings depending on the severity of the disease. The loss of sensory nerves of the nasal cavity

reduces local sensations, also the older age patients who are being neglected in families, inability to maintain good hygiene, this cumulative effect makes the patient unaware of foul smelling nasal discharge. In addition, putrefied nasal debris attract flies (*Chrysomya* sp) may enter and lay eggs in the nose, resulting in nasal myiasis eroding the surrounding structures. [13] According to study done by kedarnath et al, [10] foul smelling nasal discharge and falling of crusts were the most common symptoms which were present in all patients (100%) followed by loss of sense of smell in 19 patients (95%), nasal obstruction in 16 patients (80%). The other symptoms were bleeding from the nose in 9 patients (45%), headache in 9 patients (45%) and maggot's infestation in 2 patients (10%). And study done by Gadre et al, [5] foul smelling Nasal discharge and crusting were present in all patients (100%). Similar findings were observed in our study. It has been reported that, anosmia can be a presenting feature in 40-90% of the patients by Datti et al. [4]

Among the nasal signs, foul smelling greenish crusts was seen in 30 (85.7%) patients, followed by roomy nasal cavity and atrophied nasal mucosa and atrophied turbinates in 28 (80%) of patients, deviated nasal septum in 25 and saddle nose deformity was seen in 6 (17%) patients.

Study done by kedarnath et al, [10] shows the most common clinical signs were crusting, roomy nasal cavity, atrophic nasal mucosa and atrophic turbinates in all 20 patients (100%). The other findings were deviated nasal septum in 5 patients (25%), septal perforation in 2 patients (10%). According to Gadre et al, [5] the most common signs were roomy nasal cavity (100%), nasal crusting (100%), and turbinate atrophy (86%). These findings observed were similar to our study.

In our study patients had undergone various modalities of treatment after a brief course of antibiotics, Alkaline nasal douching in 14 (40%)

patients, nasal douching followed by 25% glucose in glycerine nasal drops in 10 patients (28.57%), modified Young's surgery in 8 (22.8%) patients, endoscopic neoturbinate surgery in 3 (8.5%) patients. Patients were followed up for a period of 6 months.

Despite surgical counseling, majority of patients prefer nonsurgical treatment which is a common scenario observed in India. In our study most patients with predominantly mild-moderate disease refused to undergo surgery, they underwent nonsurgical treatment. The surgical arm focused mainly on the severe disease category. Some surgical candidates underwent modified Young's operation and subsequent recannulation and observation after 6 months. The modified Young's procedure permits a 1- to 2-mm residual aperture, as opposed to complete closure as in classical Young's surgery, while others underwent endoscope assisted neoturbinate creation by antral mucosal inversion. Mishra et al, [14] conducted study on interventions for atrophic rhinitis, the different interventions employed were alkaline nasal douching, glucose- glycerine nasal drops, nasal prosthesis and surgical intervention done was modified Young's surgery.

Transplantation of the maxillary sinus mucosa to the nose in the form of an evaginated bag has been attempted in seven cases of atrophic rhinitis by Sharan R et al. [15] Kedarnath et al [16] conducted study to observe results in endoscope assisted creation of neoturbinate by antral mucosal inversion in atrophic rhinitis. After treatment, the clinical profile was categorized into improvement in subjective symptoms and objective signs. The clinical response was recorded as satisfactory or unsatisfactory in resolution of the illness. The severity of the disease, improvement criteria and clinical response after treatment was classified as recommended by Ssali et al. [17]

In our study, the patients who undergone alkaline nasal douching, satisfactory response seen in 8 (57.1%) and unsatisfactory response in 6 (42.9%) patients. Among patients with nasal douching and 25% glucose in glycerine nasal drops 8 (80%) patients had satisfactory response and 2 (20%) unsatisfactory.

According to Mishra et al, [14] nonsurgical patients showed satisfactory improvement in 6 (9.8%) and unsatisfactory response in 34.4% cases which differ from our study. Among the nonsurgical patients, satisfactory response was recorded as described in the criteria, the unsatisfactory response to treatment can be attributed to possible etiological influences (i.e, genetic, metabolic, endocrinal, autoimmune, and degenerative) that becomes more important than simply mucosal atrophy, osteocartilaginous resorption, or anatomic obstruction due to dried

crusts in so-called advanced debilitating disease. Among the surgically managed patients with modified Young's surgery showed satisfactory response in 6 (75%) patients. In our study, the satisfactory response seen in modified Young's surgery is likely due to prevention of mucosal desiccation and secondary bacterial invasion, as opposed to medical management with an open nasal aperture.

According to Mishra et al, [14] surgical treatment with modified Young's surgery was significantly associated with better clinical improvement, it is likely more effective in resolving local conditions with associated recurrent infections. Endoscopic neoturbinate surgery showed satisfactory response in 2 (66.6%) patients and unsatisfactory response in 1 patient. On clinical examination, at 6 months follow-up period, regression in the size of the neoturbinate was noted in 1 patient. With regression, crusts were seen. Another group of 2 patients showed no regression in the size of the neoturbinate. In these patients there was no crusting in the nose with a pink mucosa and normal turbinates. It has been seen in our study that, those of the cases where a wider bolgerization of the mucoperiosteal bag to the septum was made, did not show regression.

According to Kedarnath et al, [15] successful outcome seen in creating a neoturbinate in 12 patients (60%). Improvement in their symptoms was noted in all the patients. Excellent results were obtained in 4 patients (20%), good in 2 patients (10%), considering only the bolgerized cases, which is similar to our study.

Conclusion

Atrophic rhinitis is a chronic distressing condition, incurable yet not fatal. In spite of tireless efforts, the code of its etiology still remains unexplained. Many theories and hypotheses are put forth to explain this condition but have failed to catch general acceptance. The diagnosis of atrophic rhinitis was based on clinical characteristics like fetor, greenish crusts, roomy nasal cavities, epistaxis and cacosmia. Management of the disease was done with various medical therapeutic regimens and various surgical procedures. Complete cure of the disease is not yet possible due to the underlying immunologic state. Surgical options for the condition are also not completely satisfactory.

Hence, it is important to maintain adequate lubrication, local hygiene and proper management with regular follow-up to determine a true improvement. Further studies are required for long-term benefits or risks of different treatment modalities for atrophic rhinitis.

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